

To Develop and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Estimation of Mycophenolate Mofetil in Pure and Pharmaceutical Tablet Dosage

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Abstract

The present work is aimed at development and validation of RP HPLC method which is simple, specific, precise, and accurate for estimation of Mycophenolate Mofetil and its process-related impurity in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. Extensive literature survey revealed no method for estimation of the above said. The characterization of synthesized impurities detected by using FTIR, NMR and MS. The RP-HPLC method was developed according to ICH Q2B guidelines for quantitation of impurity in bulk and formulations. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines. The method was found to be linear, precise, accurate, robust and rugged. The present study focuses on the various steps, parameters involved in HPLC condition. Various applications of this system also discussed. HPLC process development is important in case of drug discovery, drug development and pharmaceutical products. It can be adopted apparently for routine quality control study of research and formulation tests. The method is carried out on a Symmetry C18 (4.6 mm ID × 150 mm, 5 μm, Make: X-Terra) with a mobile phase consisting of acetonitrile and potassium di-hydrogen phosphate buffer of pH=4.0 in the ratio 65:35 volume/ volume at a flow rate of 0.7mL/min. The detection of eluted components is carried out at a wavelength of 216 nm. The retention time of mycophenolate mofetil is found to be 2.647min. The developed method is validated in terms of accuracy, precision, linearity, limit of detection, limit of quantization. The linearity limits, LOD and LOQ of the developed method are found to be 10-50, 0.052 and 0.171 μg mL⁻¹, respectively. The developed method is found to be simple, fast and economic and hence it can be used as an alternative method in quality control.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, Mycophenolate mofetil, Impurities, Guidelines, Symmetry.

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Introduction

Mycophenolate mofetil (MMF) is an immunosuppressant and prodrug of mycophenolic acid, used extensively in transplant medicine. It is a reversible inhibitor of inosine monophosphate

dehydrogenase1 (IMPDH) in purine biosynthesis, more specifically guanine synthesis, which is necessary for the growth of T cells and B cells. Mycophenolate mofetil is also used in the treatment of

autoimmune diseases, such as Behcet's disease, pemphigus vulgaris and systemic lupus erythematosus. The chemical name for mycophenolate mofetil is 2-morpholinoethyl (E)-6-(1,3-dihydro-4-hydroxy-6-methoxy-7-methyl-3-oxo-5-isobenzofuranyl)-4-methyl-4-hexenoate. Its empirical formula is C₂₃H₃₁NO₇ with molecular weight 433.50 and soluble in acidic medium. It is available in the brand names such as CellCept, Myfortic. [1-2]

The identification and qualification of impurities in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient's (API's) and pharmaceutical products, is a very intensive activity performed at many levels of the drug discovery and beyond. Impurities related to starting materials, by-products, breakdown products or polymorphs. They can appear at the API production level as well as during or after formulation process. Impurities in APIs are of significant concern as they may carry activity responsible for the eventual undesirable side effects or toxicity and/or may interfere with the drug's activity. Thus monitoring impurities in API and drug product is a prerequisite to insure drug safety and quality. In Pharmaceutical World, an impurity is considered as any other organic materials, besides the drug substances, or ingredients, arises out of synthesis or unwanted chemicals that remains with Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient's (API's). The impurity may be developed either during formulation or upon aging of both API's and formulations. Presence of impurities in trace quantity in drug substance or drug product is inevitable. Therefore, their level should be controlled and monitored. They reinforce or diminish the pharmacological efficacy of the Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient's. [1] ICH defines impurities profile of a drug

materials is "A description of the identified and unidentified impurities, present in a new drug substance." For Pharmaceutical products, impurities are defined as "substance in the product that are not the API itself or the excipient used to manufacture it" i.e. impurities are unwanted chemical that remains within the formulation or API in small amounts which can influence Quality, Safety and Efficacy, thereby causing serious health hazards. [2] Qualification of the impurities is the process of acquiring and evaluating data that establishes biological safety of an individual impurity; thus, revealing the need and scope of impurity profiling of drugs in pharmaceutical research. [3] Identification of impurities is done by a variety of Chromatographic and Spectroscopic techniques, either alone or in combination with other techniques. [3-5]

Methodology and Experimental Work:

The author had developed a liquid chromatographic in bulk samples and pharmaceutical formulations. In this study PEAK 7000 isocratic HPLC with rheodine manual sample injector with switch (77251) was employed and the column used was thermohypersil BDS C18 (250 mmx4.6 mm, particle size 5 µm) column, Waters 2695 alliance with binary HPLC pump and a Waters 2998 PDA detector. Waters Empower 2 software was used for monitoring chromatographic analysis and data acquisition. Spectra lab DGA 20 A3 ultrasonic bath sonicator was used for degassing the mobile phase. Electronic balance ELB 300 was used for weighing the materials. The syringe used for injecting was 20 µL Hamilton syringe. DIGISUN pH meter was used for all pH measurements.

Sample preparation:

Accurately weighed Quantity of sample powder equivalent to 10 mg of Mycophenolate Mofetil was transferred into 100 mL of volumetric flask added 50mL of water and sonicated for 30 mins and make up the volume with mobile phase and filtered through the 0.45 μm membrane filter paper. 5 mL of the above solution is taken into 25 mL volumetric flask make up the volume with mobile phase. An aliquot of this solution was injected into HPLC system.

Method Development and Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions: In order to develop the method, a study base line was recorded with the optimized chromatographic conditions set for Mycophenolate Mofetil and stabilized for about 30 minutes. A non-polar C18 column was chosen as the stationary phase for this study. The following studies were carried for this purpose.

Mobile Phase: For getting sharp peak and line separation of the components, successive aliquots of the sample solution were recorded by the author until the

reproducibility of the peak areas was adequate.

For ideal separation of the drug isocratic conditions, mixtures of commonly used solvents with or without different buffers in different combinations were tested as mobile phases on C18 stationary phase. A mixture of 0.01 M sodium acetate solution and methanol in the ratio of 600: 400 (v/v) was found to be the most suitable of all the combinations since the chromatographic peaks were better defined, resolved and showed a low tailing factor of 1.622 for Mycophenolate Mofetil. The analysis was carried at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The injecting volume is 20 μL and the total run time 7 minutes.

Detection Wavelength: UV-spectrophotometer was used to record the spectra of diluted solution of Mycophenolate Mofetil in methanol. The peaks of maximum absorbance wavelengths were observed. The spectra of the Mycophenolate Mofetil showed that a balanced wavelength was found to be 216 nm.

Fig 1: Standard chromatogram for Mycophenolate Mofetil

Table 1: Optimized Chromatographic conditions

S. No	Parameter	Value
1	Column	Inertsil- ODS C18 (250 mmx4.6 mm, particle size 5 μm)
2	Mobile phase	water (pH 5.2 adjusted with sodium acetate) and methanol in the ratio of 600: 400(v/v)

3	Flow rate	1.0 mL/min
4	Diluent	Mobile phase
5	Column temperature	25°C
6	pH	5.2
7	API Concentration	Mycophenolate Mofetil - 20 µg/mL
8	Run time	6 min
9	Retention time	Mycophenolate Mofetil -1.4 min.
10	Volume of injection	10 µL
11	Detection wave length	216 nm

Table 2: Linearity data of Mycophenolate Mofetil

S.No	Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak area	
1	10	1877189	Slope = 37490 C.C = 0.99 (~1.0)
2	15.00	2812563	
3	20.00	3747683	
4	25	4688354	
5	30	5621489	

Fig. 2: Chromatograms of Linearity for Mycophenolate Mofetil.**Table 3: Intra – day precision of Mycophenolate Mofetil**

S. No	Sample Weight (mg)	Mycophenolate Mofetil	% Assay Mycophenolate Mofetil
1	482.20	3746397	99
2	482.20	3746266	99
3	482.20	3741869	99
4	482.20	3740761	99
5	482.20	3740569	99
6	482.20	3749990	99
Average			99

Assay:			
STD			0.10
%RSD			0.10

Table 4: Inter – day precision of Mycophenolate Mofetil

S.No	Sample Weight (mg)	Mycophenolate Mofetil	% Assay Mycophenolate Mofetil
1	482.20	3746548	99
2	482.20	3745985	99
3	482.20	3746892	99
4	482.20	3748657	99
5	482.20	3746829	99
6	482.20	3748219	99
Average Assay:			99
STD			0.03
%RSD			0.03

Fig.3: Accuracy Chromatograms-50% of Mycophenolate Mofetil

Table 5: Accuracy data of Mycophenolate Mofetil

Spiked Level	Sample Weight (mg)	Sample Area	$\mu\text{g/mL}$ added	$\mu\text{g/mL}$ found	% recovery	mean
50%	241.50	1875005	9.910	9.92	100.10 (~100)	100.04 (~100)
50%	241.50	1875013	9.910	9.92	100.10 (~100)	
50%	241.50	1879474	9.910	9.94	100.30 (~100)	
50%	241.50	1871012	9.910	9.90	99.89 (~100)	
50%	241.50	1870158	9.910	9.89	99.79 (~100)	
50%	241.50	1876423	9.910	9.92	100.10 (~100)	
100%	483.00	3747599	19.820	19.82	100.00 (~100)	99.99 (~100)
100%	483.00	3745976	19.820	19.81	99.94 (~100)	
100%	483.00	3749990	19.820	19.83	100.05 (~100)	
150%	725.00	5626444	29.751	29.76	100.03 (~100)	99.99 (~100)
150%	725.00	5623774	29.751	29.75	99.99 (~100)	
150%	725.00	5620015	29.751	29.73	99.92 (~100)	
150%	725.00	5624450	29.751	29.75	99.99 (~100)	
150%	725.00	5626008	29.751	29.76	100.03 (~100)	
150%	725.00	5626410	29.751	29.76	100.03 (~100)	

Fig4: Accuracy Chromatograms-100% of Mycophenolate Mofetil

Table 6: Ruggedness of Mycophenolate Mofetil

Injection number	Peak area
1	3742362
2	3740123
3	3739472
4	3720912
5	3701634
6	3692345
7	3681204
Mean	3716864.5714
SD	23370.9432
% RSD	0.62878

Table 7: Robustness data of Mycophenolate Mofetil

S No	Sample name	Change	Name	RT	Area	Tailing	Plate count
1	Flow1	0.2 mL/min (1.0-0.2)	Mycophenolate Mofetil	1.827	4646829	1.524	2701
2	Flow2	0.2 mL/min (1.0+0.2)	Mycophenolate Mofetil	1.294	2973403	1.541	2932
3	Temp1	5oC (25-5)	Mycophenolate Mofetil	1.444	3674010	1.586	2788
4	Temp2	5oC (25+5)	Mycophenolate Mofetil	1.439	3689369	1.580	2652

Table 8: Estimation of Mycophenolate Mofetil from its formulation

Formulation	Dosage	Sample conc. $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Sample Area	Amount Found $\mu\text{g/mL}$	% assay
Seromune	Mycophenolate Mofetil	20	3747649.1	19.98	99.9

SUMMARY OF WORK

The overall results obtained for the proposed method validation were tabulated in Table 9.

Table 9: Summary of the proposed method validation

S.No	Test parameter	Result
1	Linearity (correlation coefficient)	M- 0.99 (~1.0)
2	Precession (%RSD) a) Intra-day b) Inter-day	M- 0.10 M-0.03
3	Accuracy (% drug substance)	M- 100.00
4	LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	M- 0.050
5	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	M- 0.167

To obtain suitable mobile phase combination of methanol and 1% sodium acetate were tested for the analysis of the selected drug combination. Finally the 0.01 M sodium acetate solution and Mycophenolate Mofetil in the ratio of 600:400 (v/v) as mobile phase was give symmetric peak at 216 nm in short runtime (6 min). The pH was maintained at 5.2 and the chromatogram obtained for the mobile phase has been showed good affinity towards Mycophenolate Mofetil. Retention time =1.4 min which were similar to the earlier reported methods. The literature survey on various HPLC methods available suggest that a low tailing factor of 1.622 for Mycophenolate Mofetil, was obtained by using a mixture of 0.01 M sodium acetate solution and methanol in the ratio of 600: 400 (v/v) as

mobile phase

Conclusions

The statistical evaluation of the proposed method revealed its good linearity, reproducibility and its validation for different parameters made us to conclude that the current RP-HPLC method can successfully be used for reliable determination of Mycophenolate Mofetil in pharmaceutical dosage form and also in bulk drug. The developed method was found specific to the drug and for dosage form because no interfering material peaks near the drug peak were observed in the chromatograms obtained in the study runtime.

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